

SULFUR CONCENTRATION IN COKE

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Abstract. This study investigates the sulfur concentration in coke and the factors influencing its formation. During the coking process, a portion of sulfur is released into the gas phase in the form of H_2S , while the remaining part is distributed between coke and distillate products. The results show that the sulfur content in coke strongly depends on the feedstock composition and process conditions, with higher concentrations observed in heavy fractions. The obtained conclusions confirm the importance of optimizing technological parameters to control coke quality.

Keywords: coke, sulfur, coking, heavy petroleum residues, H_2S .

When heavy petroleum residues are directly introduced into the coking process, sulfur-containing compounds in the feedstock first undergo thermal decomposition reactions. During this process, a portion of sulfur is released into the gas phase in the form of hydrogen sulfide (H_2S), while the remaining fraction is distributed among the resulting products, including liquid fractions and solid coke.

Studies show that under coking conditions, up to approximately 30% of sulfur may transfer to the gas phase. However, in secondary processed feedstocks, this value is significantly lower, averaging around 12%. This indicates a strong dependence on both the composition of the feedstock and its degree of prior processing.

The major portion of sulfur is distributed between the solid (coke) and liquid (distillate) products. In particular, during coking of straight-run feedstocks, a considerable share of sulfur accumulates in the coke phase, reaching up to 70% of the total sulfur distribution. For secondary-origin feedstock components, this value is even higher, increasing up to 90%. This clearly demonstrates that the degree of sulfur enrichment in coke is strongly dependent on the nature of the feedstock [1; 112 pp.].

Furthermore, the distribution of sulfur in the resulting distillate fractions is directly related to their boiling point range. As the transition occurs from lighter fractions to heavier gas oil fractions, the sulfur concentration increases significantly. In heavy gas oil fractions, this increase continues; however, the rate of growth becomes comparatively slower. Therefore, the main accumulation of sulfur in coking products is observed in heavy fractions and in the coke phase.

Based on the results presented in Figure 2, it can be stated that experimental studies carried out on tar samples obtained from the primary crude oil distillation units of the “Fergana Oil Refinery” LLC empirically confirm the observed regularities in the distribution of sulfur within liquid and non-coked products.

Figure 3 presents data on the distribution of sulfur in distillate fractions obtained from coking experiments carried out under the conditions of the “Fergana Oil Refinery” LLC using tar-based feedstock. The obtained results indicate that the coking process conducted under elevated pressure has a significant influence on the group-chemical composition of the distillate products [2; 165-pp.].

In particular, heavy fractions with a boiling point above 350 °C are characterized by a reduced content of paraffin-naphthenic and light aromatic hydrocarbons compared to processes carried out under atmospheric pressure conditions. At the same time, an increase in the relative proportion of paraffin-naphthenic hydrocarbons is observed in the gasoline fractions, indicating a redistribution of components during the process.

Furthermore, experimental results confirm that an increase in the density of heavy petroleum residues is directly associated with a higher content of paraffin-naphthenic, medium aromatic hydrocarbons, and resinous compounds. This reflects a clear interdependence between the physicochemical properties of the feedstock and the composition of the resulting products [3; 10-12 pp.].

In addition, Figures 4 and 5 demonstrate a high degree of agreement between experimental data and modeled predictive values for sulfur content and density in heavy fractions, presented in graphical form. This close correlation confirms the reliability and accuracy of the developed computational models.

4-pic - Sulfur content in heavy gas oil

5-pic- Density of heavy gas oil

Coking and Quality Indicators of Heavy Petroleum Products from Coking

Table 1

Experiment number	Heavy petroleum product 350 °C — к.к.		Coke		
	Sulfur content, %	Density, g/cm ³	Sulfur content, %	Volatile matter content%	Density, g/cm ³
1	0,91	0,987	0,57	5,1	0,110
2	0,95	0,972	0,54	5,2	0,105
3	0,97	0,969	0,52	5,3	0,100
4	1,05	0,997	0,65	4,8	0,115
5	1,02	0,971	0,51	4,2	0,095

Changes in the Physicochemical Properties of Coked Distillate

Table 2

Name	Boiling point of fractions, °C			
	200-250	250-300	300-350	350-к.к.
Coking capacity, mass %.	0,950	0,973	0,978	0,994
Sulfur content, mass %	0,06	0,11	0,23	0,48.
Name	0,18	0,22	0,38	0,73
Chemical group composition, % by mass				
Paraffinic-naphthenic hydrocarbons	38,2	29,7	28,0	23,2
Light aromatic hydrocarbons	4,4	9,6	11,8	5,5
Medium aromatic hydrocarbons	26,5	25,0	14,5	5,7
Heavy aromatic hydrocarbons	30,4	34,8	40,6	59,4
Resins	0,5	0,9	5,1	6,2

Based on the analysis of the data presented in Table 2, it can be stated that with an increasing depth of separation of the recycle fraction from coking

distillates, the physicochemical properties of the resulting fractions undergo significant changes. In particular, a gradual increase in density, sulfur content, and coke-forming tendency (coking propensity) of the fractions is observed. This behavior can be explained by the accumulation of heavy components in the system and a corresponding decrease in their thermal stability.

At the same time, a decrease in the content of paraffin-naphthenic hydrocarbons and aromatic compounds with medium molecular mass is recorded. In contrast, the proportion of heavy aromatic hydrocarbons increases, indicating that these components act as the primary precursors in the coke formation process.

The results also show that the highest concentration of light aromatic hydrocarbons is observed in the fraction boiling within the 300–350 °C range, where their mass fraction reaches 11.8% [4;5; 46,47–8,9 pp.]. The composition of this fraction is of particular importance for understanding the redistribution of aromatic structures during coking and the mechanisms of sulfur compound accumulation in heavier phases.

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